

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF PSYCHOLOGY

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Annotation: *this article focuses on a brief history of psychology, who studied it. At the same time, the directions of modern psychology are mentioned.*

Keywords: *psychology, mental stage, experimental psychology, laboratory of psychology, mental state of humans, degree of development of the soul, karma, chakras.*

The history of psychology, like any other science, is an interesting and meaningful field of knowledge. The history of psychology is the history of the gradual accumulation of knowledge about the mental life phenomena characteristic of animals and humans by mankind. It is the process of collecting and deepening the knowledge of a person about himself. As we get acquainted with the history of psychology, we will learn how the desire to study the mental life of people and animals was shaped by their theoretical and practical needs at various historical stages, and how some laws were discovered. The history of psychology also provides information about how the field of psychological knowledge expanded in the stages of historical life, in connection with the general development of science and culture, and how psychology, which was the only one at the beginning, developed and rose to the level of a whole system of psychological sciences. The history of psychology provides an opportunity to know the psyche more deeply and clearly. Research and creation of useful scientific research methods that contribute to the development of the science of psychology is of great importance.

Since ancient times, people have been trying to find answers to questions about themselves, and at the same time, related to the mental processes taking place in their inner world. And this in turn led to the foundation of the science of psychology that we love to study. Psychology is a wonderful science. At the same time, it is both young and one of the oldest sciences. The term "psychology" literally means the science of the soul (Psyche - soul; logos = science).

In the past, psychology was part of metaphysics and dealt with the nature, origin and destiny of the soul. It was called rational psychology. But modern psychology is empirical and does not deal with the problems of the soul [3]. Already ancient philosophers thought about problems that are personal to modern psychology. The soul and its interconnectedness, perception, memory and thinking issues; education and upbringing, emotions and motivation of human behavior and many other questions were put forward by scholars in the 6th and 7th centuries BC after the first philosophical schools appeared in Greece. But the old thinkers were not psychos in the modern sense. The symbolic birthday of psychology is 1879, the year Wilhelm Wundt discovered the first experimental laboratory in Leipzig, Germany. Until then, psychology remained a speculative science.

And only V. Wundt took the liberty of combining psychology and experiment. For Wundt, psychology was the science of consciousness. In 1881, the Institute of Experimental Psychology was opened on the basis of a laboratory (it still exists), which became a state scientific center, but also an international center of psychologists.

During the Renaissance, Leonardo da Vinci, X. Vives contributed to the development of psychology. By the 18th century, M.V. Lomonosov, A.N. Radishchev, G. S. Skovoroda, T. Hobbes, B. Spinoza, G. Leibniz, J. Locke, K. A. Gelvetsii, P. A. Holbach, D. Diderot made many discoveries in psychology, enriching it with practical information. In the development of psychology, the experiments of the 19th century were of particular importance. During this period, a set of methods was used to study the psychological reality: observation, laboratory experiment, natural experiment, analysis of activity results, genetic method of modeling mental processes, test, expert assessment, interview, questionnaire, biography, etc. At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, a number of psychological scientific schools and trends emerged: behaviorism, Gestalt psychology, personalism, Freudianism, etc. The teachings of I. M. Sechenov (reflective nature of the psyche), I. P. Pavlov (higher nervous activity) made an important contribution to the development of psychology. In Russia, V. M. Bekhterev's experimental laboratory (Kazon, 1885), Kharkov University and N. N. Lange's laboratory in Odessa, G. Chelpanov's laboratory in Kiev, S. Korsakov's in Moscow, later V. M. Bekhterev's, A. Lazursky's, A. Nechayev's in Petersburg, V. Chizh's Yuryev (Tartu , Estonia) had a special impact on the development of psychology. In 1912, the Institute of Psychology was opened at Moscow University. In the same year, I. A. Sikorsky established the Institute of Child Psychology for the first time in the world in Kiev. In the first half of the 20th century in Russia, K. N. Kornilov, P. P. Blonsky and other psychologists began to create scientific psychology based on dialectics.

Modern psychology is considered a science consisting of a multidisciplinary system of psychological knowledge, consisting of many fields with its own research subject: general psychology, aviation psychology, military psychology, differential psychology, psychophysiology, engineering psychology, space psychology, legal psychology, medical psychology, neuropsychology, pathopsychology, educational psychology, labor psychology, sports psychology, special psychology, creative psychology, management psychology, marketing psychology, social psychology, youth psychology, organizational psychology, religious psychology, family psychology, history of psychology, genetic psychology, applied psychology, experimental psychology, the main reason for the division of professional psychology, psycholinguistics, political psychology and other psychology into branches is the emergence of applied fields in its structure. Psychology is actively involved in solving important issues in industry, community management, education system, health care, culture, sports, transport, radio, television and other structures. The achievements of psychology are of particular importance in the realization of individual potentials and their activation, and thus have an impact on increasing labor efficiency. In modern psychology, electronic computing techniques, electrical and chemical tools are used to study the psyche in depth. In psychology, several methods are used to study a person, his mental experiences, stages of development, and cognitive activity. One of them,

the method of self-observation (introspection), continues to be fiercely debated. Some psychologists emphasize it as the main method of conducting research, while others recognize its limitations and recommend using objective methods instead. Thanks to objective methods, the material basis of the psyche has been determined, and it has been proven that the causal connection of subjective states with human internal relations is manifested in an individual and in a group. In the world community, psychological research is conducted on a large scale in scientific research institutes and centers, universities in the USA, England, France, Germany, Russia, and Switzerland.

Over time, the dimensions of the Earth changed, along with a new direction - the direction of esotericism, which includes concepts such as the spiritual dimensions of people, the level of development of the soul, karma, chakras. appeared. Although this direction is not scientifically and practically based, today the world's leading and most advanced psychologists are working in this direction and it remains useful for people who need psychological help.

In conclusion, it can be said that the science of the human psyche, that is, psychology, is a leading science that has retained its place and importance in terms of its usefulness and interest to people not only in the years before our era, but also at the time of the development of information technologies and social networks. is one of the directions. For humans, the science of psychology will retain its leading position and importance in the near future, since every person has a strong desire to gain self-awareness at the stage of development and growth and thereby further develop himself.

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